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XALQARO JURNALI**

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TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA ЯЗЫК, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ПЕРЕВОД LANGUAGE, EDUCATION, TRANSLATION

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MEDIA LINGUISTICS AS A TOPICAL ISSUE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK CONTEMPORARY LINGUISTICS

ABSTRACT

This fast-paced world has been making a remarkable shift with the advancement of Internet in media sphere. This article provides theoretically strengthened frameworks and appropriate analyses on media, its integral part – media text, and their linguistic features with the comparison of English and Uzbek languages. The study highlights differences between traditional and digital media, especially in the language use, the degree of formality and paralinguistic features which is more interesting that notable cultural nuances, variabilities in two nations – English and Uzbek – can also be found as a result. The research identifies that while old media, including TV, newspaper and radio mostly relies on formality, Internet media is attracting its users by novel informal characters: the usage of non-verbal signs, namely emojis, GIFs, stickers or memes which are not stopping going viral and appealing the audience unbelievably day by day.

Key words: media linguistics, media text, traditional media, digital media, Internet linguistics, multimodal signs, emojis, polycode phenomena.

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INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIGIDA MEDIALINGVISTIKA DOLZARB MASALA SIFATIDAGI O'RNI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu ilg'or zamon, ayniqsa internetning jadal rivojlanuvi media sohasiga sezilarli ta'sir o'tkazmay qo'ymadi. Ushbu maqola media, uning muhim tarkibiy qismi hisoblangan media matn, ularning lisoniy xususiyatlari haqida ingliz va o'zbek tillari qiyoslanishi asosida kuchli

ilmiy nazariyalar hamda tahlillar bilan baham ko'radi. Tadqiqot an'anaviy va raqamli media o'rtasidagi o'zaro farqlar, ayniqsa til qo'llanilishi, rasmiylik darajasi va paralingvistik xususiyatlarni o'rganib, alohida urg'u beradi va natijada, ikki millat – ingliz va o'zbek – orasidagi madaniy nuanslar va xilma-xilliklar ham ko'zga tashlanishi tabiiy. Izlanish natijasiga ko'ra shu aniqlanadiki, televizor, gazeta va radio kabilarni o'z ichiga oluvchi eski media ko'p hollarda rasmiylikka tayanadigan bo'lsa, Internet media aksincha, ya'ni o'zining yangi turdagi norasmiy xususiyatlari bilan foydalanuvchilarni jalb qilib kelmoqda: ayniqsa, kundan-kunga dolzarb bo'lib borayotgan va auditoriyani ishonib bo'lmas darajada qiziqtirib kelayotgan emoji, GIF, stiker, mem kabi nolisoniy belgilar kundan-kunga dolzarb bo'lib borishi bilan bir qatorda, auditoriyani ishonib bo'lmas darajada qiziqtirib kelmoqda.

Tayanch so'zlar: media tilshunoslik, media matn, an'anaviy media, raqamli media, Internet tilshunosligi, multimodal belgilar, emojilar, polikod hodisasi.

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МЕДИА-ЛИНГВИСТИКА КАК АКТУАЛЬНЫЙ ВОПРОС В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ АНГЛИЙСКОЙ И УЗБЕКСКОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В современном быстро меняющемся мире происходят значительные изменения благодаря развитию интернета в медиасфере. В данной статье представлены теоретически обоснованные концепции и соответствующий анализ медиа, их неотъемлемой части – медиатекста, и их лингвистических особенностей на примере английского и узбекского языков. Исследование выявляет различия между традиционными и цифровыми медиа, особенно в использовании языка, степени формальности и паралингвистических особенностях, что особенно интересно, поскольку в результате можно обнаружить заметные культурные нюансы и вариативность в двух странах – английском и узбекском. Исследование показывает, что в то время как старые медиа, включая телевидение, газеты и радио, в основном опираются на формальность, интернет-медиа привлекают пользователей новыми неформальными способами: использованием невербальных знаков, а именно эмодзи, GIF-файлов, стикеров или мемов, которые с каждым днем становятся все более вирусными и невероятно привлекательными для аудитории.

Ключевые слова: медиалингвистика, медиатекст, традиционные медиа, цифровые медиа, интернет-лингвистика, мультимодальные знаки, эмодзи, поликодовые явления.

In today's world, of paramount significance mass media is not only journalism but also in linguistics, as media is influencing both social and cultural factors, how individuals interact with each other or how communication factors are being shifted due to media. Significantly, the new discipline – media linguistics emerged on the basis of anthropocentric paradigm in the late 20th century due to the fact that media started widely affect language norms the society used

with the help of technology advancements, and this branch addresses how media might have an impact on language, society and culture at all. Before the emergence of media linguistics, there were also discussions and debates on the relationship between media and language in the middle of 20th century by particular scholars as van Dijk and Fowler, however, in the late of 20th century it was appeared as an independent field. It is notable that the term 'media linguistics' can be initially found through the work of Tatiana Dobrosklonskaya who is a noticeable linguist professor in Russia. She defines that media linguistics investigates both linguistic and non-linguistic factors, considering not only final or ready material itself, but also what kind of responses might be expected from the audience as well. According to this statement, it is clear that media includes verbal signs (words, grammar, dialogues, tone of voice) as well as non-verbal (body language, facial expressions, visuals), and besides that in addition to the type of pragmatic intention, addressees' reaction to the message is simultaneously crucial. Similar to this idea, Perrin [28, B.42] explains media language is a tool for media professionals to get the audience the message and interpret it in a proper way. Obviously, people in the media scope deliberately utilize the language to perform a kind of speech act which is the target as informing, congratulating or warning with requiring public to get it as intended which is called perlocutionary act that is completed by the society. Furthermore, Lueger et al. [24, B.14] highlight mostly how media shows cultural aspects of society with the help of platforms (newspapers, TV, radio, advertising, and online publications) via language. Since language is considered as an integral part of culture, media language also illustrates a piece of culture somehow. Whereas scholars' definitions on media linguistics vary, they all emphasize an interdisciplinary character of this discipline. In fact, both Bell [3, B.69] and van Dijk [31, B.226] support the idea of that field of media is correspondingly connected with sociolinguistics, pragma linguistics, psychology, linguoculturology that are being developed under the anthropocentric paradigm which put humanity to the center. Indeed, the anthropocentric approach serves as a tool for human communication, prioritizing the roles of the sender and addressee in speech interaction [17, B.33]. Therefore, media linguistics is also relevant to this idea, as it also assists to convey ideas, thoughts and information through media tools. Adopting a similar framework, Dobrosklonskaya [9, B.57] argues that it is impossible to deeply understand media linguistics without attaching other modern linguistics disciplines, because media language is not merely about words and language signs, or just sending a message to the sender. There are other factors beyond words that render this area media linguistics: multimodality, images, sounds, background features, tenor. Then, why is media linguistics linked with sociolinguistics, cultural studies, pragmatics or psychology? Initially, sociology prevent structures and frames on the role of media in shaping social norms, identities, while psychology offers insights of how the public interprets information media provides or how media controls emotion and attitudes in human brain. Furthermore, linguoculturology investigates the relationship of three key components – media, language and culture, mostly emphasizing the issues of representation, power, and ideology. Besides, pragmatics deals with which contextual meaning or pragmatic intention is used in media discourse. It is speech act theory which bounds both pragma and media linguistics together. Through the media text media representatives do not just write or speak particular information, they carry out a distinct speech act.

Media discourse cannot be imagined without the media text elements that constitute it, because it is media text which is a key element to identify how the speaker uses language to achieve his/her pragmatic intention, and which type of media text corresponds to a particular speech act. As time passes or due to the rapidity of developments, it is clear that a significant semantic shift can be appeared in language, and this means that media text types also take on different forms and change as the media field develops, which paves the way for innovations and novelties that can be made in the field of media linguistics. However, the connotation of media text is wider than traditional understanding of the text which only consists of verbal signs. This indicates that media styles classified above – old and new – encompass media texts, depending on their aims and objectives. As Dobrosklonskaya [9, B.47] emphasizes, the media text is a *polycode phenomenon* that combines verbal, visual and auditory components, reflecting the multimodal nature of modern communication. The function of media text is not solely to use linguistic signs as words to deliver the addresser's message, conversely, applying multimodal components, including visual, graphic or auditory elements are more creative and understandable to interpret according to Dobrosklonskaya. In particular, media texts do not just serve as a linguistic message; they are also the manifestation of social and cultural life of public shaped by technological, ideological and pragmatic factors. In contemporary linguistics, the media text is viewed as one of the most important objects of study, especially with the rise of mass communication and digital technologies. In general terms, a media text can be described as a communicative product that expresses social, cultural and ideological meanings through language and other semiotic resources. As noted by Dobrosklonskaya [9, B.65], such texts represent *polycode phenomena*, since they combine verbal and non-verbal elements – words, visuals, sound and design – within a single message. This idea shows that meaning in media is created not only by linguistic means but also through their interaction with visual and auditory forms. Researchers such as Fairclough [10, B.72] and van Dijk [31, B.230] also argue that media texts should be analyzed as a type of social discourse where power, ideology and communication might cross. Because of this interdisciplinary character, the study of media texts draws upon linguistics, semiotics, sociology, and cultural studies. In this way, a media text can be seen as a living and dynamic unit that mirrors the stylistic and ideological tendencies of modern communication. The concept of a *media text* has become one of the key notions in modern linguistics, communication studies, and media analysis. Scholars often use the notion “media text” to describe any communicative product created and distributed through mass media channels such as television, newspapers, radio, or digital platforms. In its broadest sense, a media text refers to a message produced within the system of mass communication that reflects social, cultural, ideological and pragmatic meanings. In fact, both linguistic and non-linguistic media texts are the unit of a specific nation that can evoke social or cultural association on human mind. As Dobrosklonskaya [9, B.84] notes a media text is “a special form of text organization which functions in the media sphere and performs the task of informing, influencing and entertaining the target audience.” This definition emphasizes that a media text has both *informative* and *evaluative* functions, serving as a means of transmitting knowledge while shaping public opinion, and simultaneously it can perform several speech acts.

From the linguistic point of view, media texts possess specific structural, stylistic and functional characteristics. They are distinguished by their **interdisciplinary nature**, combining linguistic features typical of journalism, public communication and everyday speech.

According to Fairclough [10, B.92], media texts are the part of a broader process of *discourse practice* that connects text production, distribution and consumption. This means that any media text is not only a product of language use but also a social act that reflects power relations and ideology. Additionally, van Dijk [31, B.227] also points out that media discourse has a strong social influence: it organizes information in a way that shapes the audience's perception of reality. Thus, the media text can be viewed as a complex unit of both linguistic form and social function. One of the main features of a media text is its **multifunctional character**. It can inform, persuade, entertain and sometimes manipulate, depending on its communicative purpose. In fact, scholars such as Montgomery [27, B.56] and Bell [3, B.44] suggest that media language is a hybrid system combining features of spoken and written communication, formal and informal styles, and factual and evaluative modes of expression. This hybridity makes media texts highly adaptable to different audiences and contexts. Furthermore, the media text is characterized by its **intertextuality** – the way it refers to or reuses elements of other texts, genres, or cultural codes. Intertextuality connects media messages to shared cultural knowledge, allowing audiences to interpret them within a wider socio-cultural framework.

Modern researchers also pay attention to the **multimodal** nature of media texts. In traditional mass media, such as print newspapers, the verbal code dominates, but it is often supported by photographs, layout, color and typographic choices. In digital media, multimodality becomes even more significant, as texts combine language, sound, moving images, hyperlinks and emojis. Likewise, Kress et al. [21, B.88] argue that meaning in media communication arises from the interaction between different semiotic modes which together might create a unified communicative effect. Therefore, a media text cannot be analyzed only at the linguistic level – it requires attention to its visual, auditory and contextual aspects. It is worthy to mention once again that the multimodal nature of media text distinguishes it from other text types. Nowadays, communication types consisting mainly of linguistic signs are rarely seen in modern media texts, instead, messages consisting of images, videos and background voices are very well received by the public, because the information they convey is both interesting and effective. Dobrosklonskaya [9, B.92] also emphasizes that the polycode nature of media text through the use of both verbal and non-verbal signs is its greatest achievement, since the creation of a speech act with a whole semantic meaning through both multimodal components and linguistic elements is the mainstay of media linguistics. The notion of 'multimodality' is deeply introduced to the science by Gunther Kress and Theo van Leeuwen [21, B.27] in their works "*Reading Images: The Grammar of Visual Design and Multimodal Discourse*". According to them, contemporary communication is fully based on multimodality that consists of several semiotic signs, including sound, color or images, and each of them owns their set of resources and connotations to make a sense for creating media texts. Besides, while linguistic symbols can provide information as much as possible, non-verbal entities tend to add emotion and rhythm.

In traditional media, it can be seen that every aspect of the media text is of utmost importance in delivering the message. For example, if we analyze newspaper articles, there are enough aspects to pay attention to, from the title to the final part: the choice of font, photography and their size might strongly influence readers' interpretation. On the contrary, in broadcast media, auditory factors play a more significant role, that is, in television or radio materials, journalistic speech, interviews, background music might regulate how each word's connotation is conveyed

to the viewer. For this reason, media representatives always try to prepare speeches that affect the public, correctly select sound factors and background visualization. In short, the momentousness of multimodality in the creation of each media text and its decoding by society with this in mind is incomparable. Yet, the appearance of digital communication resulted in the shift of multimodality in media texts. In detail, emojis, Internet memes, Graphics Interchange Formats (GIFs) can be found in Internet-based media texts which made considerable intensifications in media linguistics at all. As Jewitt [19, B.124] notes, digital media environments encourage users to become *multimodal communicators* who both produce and interpret messages at the same time using diverse semiotic resources due to the fact that people are not simply reading or watching media materials, but it is public itself who both making and sharing media texts via contemporary media tools. Not only can modern aspects of media give a chance to create media texts, but also it is easier to consume information with the assistance of both verbal and non-verbal signs' mixture as well as Barthes [2, B.14] says.

When it comes to the specific types of media texts, as media linguistics can be divided into traditional and contemporary types, media text might also be conventional and modern. Accordingly, old media texts contain newspaper and magazine articles, advertisements, radio programs and television broadcast in which mostly dominates verbal expressions. Bell [3, B.89] also highlights this idea that one of the predominant types of media texts – news reporting – is principally constructed with objective modality and usually characterized by standardized grammatical structures and more neutral vocabulary. Obviously, as news style is basically established by the real facts and statistics, it is more inclined to use impartial and less stylistically-nuanced lexical resources. In contrast, Fowler [11, B.38] believes that even though news reporting style seems to be more factual and objective, the way journalists structure their stories and the words they choose inevitably shape public's interpretation of events. Whether it's the headline in a newspaper or the tone of voice on the radio, these choices influence how the audience perceives the information. Generally, news reporting is created by the following components: the headline, lead, body paragraph and conclusion, and all serve to generate whole intended message. Montgomery [27, B.59] also supports the idea of Fowler, which is on that despite the fact of news media style is appeared to use neutral language, it is not such, because its main aim to influence people's conceptual world picture, but from the view of broadcasting, therefore both scholars suppose that objectivity in news and broadcasting myth. In conjunction with this, stylistic features of traditional media is explicitly connected with its pragmatic intentions which means that for instance, the main purpose of traditional media is informing, so in order to achieve this pragmatic intention properly, other external factors beyond the words should assist, like images, music, color, face expressions and etc. Fairclough [10, B.93] argues that such extra-linguistic factors are the most powerful tools to impact the society and render them deeply understand the intended message. Hence, these aspects might differ from culture to culture: while English traditional media illustrates factual clarity and conciseness, Uzbek journalism has a great tendency to use more metaphorical language than English, preventing formality as well. Furthermore, advertisements, both in print and broadcast forms, are among the most recognizable examples of traditional media texts. They combine verbal and visual codes to achieve a persuasive effect and therefore serve as early manifestations of polycode communication. As Cook [5, B.76] and Dobrosklonskaya [9, B.109] note that advertising discourse reflects cultural values, social aspirations and ideologies, making it an important

object of linguocultural study. Additionally, advertising style differs from other media styles owing to both its objectives and linguistic devices. According to Lewis et al. [23, B.92], in order to achieve a successful advertisement, there should be following basic standards:

- attention;
- interest;
- desire;
- action.

These patterns are called 'AIDA' principle by Lewis, and although it has been more than hundred years since this principle was introduced, it still does not fail to keep its importance in advertising. Besides, Leech [22, B.118] classifies four major functions of advertisements:

1. Attention value – the utmost important aim of advertising style is being attractive to grab the audience's attention, and it is achieved by the violation of some linguistic norms, such as wrong spelling, pun, and rhyme. For example, pun: "Get Fit Done! Kettlebell Kitchen: We're weighting for your order!" This is an advertisement of meal preparing service that is called "Kettlebell Kitchen", and the stylistic device of pun is used with the help of the word 'weighting', which is connected with 'waiting', giving the idea of losing weight with healthy eating.

2. Readability – this function mostly stresses to mainstream colloquial language usage in advertising style in order to be understandable and easy to catch the meaning for consumers. It is achieved by both linguistic and extra-linguistic signs, and mainly underlines the second pronoun 'you', casual colloquial expressions, excluding formal address terms and politeness markers. One of Netflix's advertisements can be illustration of this aspect: "Binge-worthy shows? Yeah, we got a few." In this example, 'binge-worthy' is colloquialism which is used to make the target audience interested in.

3. Memorability – the message on the product in advertisement should be remembered, and for this some stylistic devices based on repetition can help, including alliteration, parallelism, rhythm: "Peter Piper Pizza: Prepared Perfectly, Priced Pretty!" This is an advertisement of Pizza organization, and in order to make their advertisement noteworthy, they use alliteration which all words begin with the same consonant 'P'.

4. Selling power – is also one of the most vital objectives that motivate people to buy the product by using imperatives, positive adjectives or expressions: "Own the Night. Command Their Gaze. Wear Aura." This is about the product of perfume and following specific terms are used to prompt the audience: imperative words – 'own', 'command', 'wear'; positive word – 'aura'.

In short, in order to complete these four functions not only expressive linguistic factors are important, but also visual images are of paramount significance to attract the target audience. They can be in the form of commercials, billboards, brochures or printed version in both oral and written type of conventional media.

The emergence of the Internet in the late twentieth century fundamentally altered the ecology of media communication. Now, when media is mentioned, it is not about just watching or reading something in newspapers, television and radio anymore. If people want, they can easily create, shift or send any media material which is called 'participatory culture', defined by Jenkins [18, B.169], and it demonstrates that media period is changing from 'passive receivers' to 'active creators'. Digital media texts encompass an enormous variety of communicative

forms, from online news and blogs to social media posts, memes, and short videos. They differ not only in format, but also in degree of interactivity, authorship and social purpose. Jewitt [19, B. 151] argues that digital communication represents a new semiotic order where meaning is co-constructed by participants in real time. Moreover, in modern media, the role of the writer and reader can be shifted, the language and linguistic terms are dynamic, and theme might differ even from hour to hour. Contemporary media incorporates social media posts, online blogs, memes, GIFs, emojis, stickers, short videos and others.

As Social media is considered to be the main means of new media, its media texts also play a crucial role. Their linguistic style is typically informal, marked by ellipsis, contractions, emoticons and creative spelling. Particularly, emojis and stickers act as non-verbal entities that replace or intensify emotional tone, thus performing functions similar to emphasize in spoken interaction. Similarly, Thurlow et al. [30, B.103] observes that these types of indications are being the reason to change the way people communicate in today's digital world due to the fact that they are the part of neither writing nor spoken communication, but they are something in between. Generally, emojis are an updated and modern form of emoticons which originally used the keyboard to produce facial expressions using characters on its own, like :) - happy, satisfied or :(- sad, dissatisfied. In contrast, emojis are not created with the help of keyboard; conversely, they are more based on pictures and graphics that are managed with Unicode [13, B.89]. Indeed, emojis are currently omnipresent in digital media to avoid the gap between communicators and deliver or decode the message in an appropriate way; especially today most people cannot imagine their online communication without any emojis or at least emoticons to express their feelings. Meanwhile, stickers are more up to date comparing to emojis, since it might combine both texts and visualizations. Besides, they are utilized by more than millions of people, and stickers can be sent instead of whole sentence or text, because the most unique aspect of them is that by mailing a relevant sticker, we may refer to the whole message [13, B.134]. Therefore, in spite of the fact that emojis and stickers are seemed to be similar and have common functions, they might differ from each other according to some nuances. When it comes to **blogs and online news portals**, they are a mixed version of both journalistic and personal discourse; accordingly, bloggers are mostly using their narrative skills in order to keep their audience by sharing personal experiences, and online news articles, meanwhile, are allowing users to explore topics more deeply with the help of images, extra-links, comment sections and so on. Another significant element of modern media texts is **GIFs which** are distinctive for their multimodal composition and humorous intent. They rely on intertextuality – reusing familiar cultural symbols, images, or phrases in new contexts to generate irony or satire. Furthermore, GIF is being used actively by public since 1990s and has already been the constitutive entity of digital communication as its features of creativity, accessibility and humor [20, B.175]. However, not always GIFs can be interpreted by the reader as an intended way according to some reasons. Initially, there might be technical barrier between the sender and receiver which means that while sending GIF, it may not show up correctly in the first place owing to digital issues. Besides that, as GIFs are the vital component of particular culture, it is possible to be cultural misunderstanding while communication [4, B.188]. In specific terms, if both addresser and addressee are not aware of culture that is sharing, it can result in problem for the sender by not achieving target reaction and the receiver also misinterpreting sender's message. Moreover, the reason why GIFs can indicate specific nation's culture is that they

normally tend to be chosen from movies, cartoons or TV shows that are belong to certain cultures [25, B.126]. It is evident that media productions as films, cartoon or other programs are produced on the basis of culture manifestations, including language tools – realias, proverbs, slangs or other symbolic characteristics. Whenever such productions are turned into GIF's, it can be clear for more popularity, and then it renders communication easier.

While contemporary media communication encompasses a wide range of text types – including blogs, comments, GIFs and social media posts – this research concentrates primarily on memes as the most expressive form of digital discourse. Memes combine verbal and visual codes, rely on humour and cultural knowledge, and vividly reflect the dynamics of speech etiquette in both English and Uzbek media spaces. In general, the term ‘meme’ was initially introduced on the analogue of the ‘gene’ by Richard Dawkins [7, B.92] in ‘The Selfish Gene’. The reason why meme is associated with biological gene is that both are ‘units of imitation’ as Dawkins [7, B.4] says. Specifically, the aims of both memes and genes are almost the same: while genes transfer biological information, memes convey cultural information. Internet opened lots of doors to ‘share, circulate, distribute, and spread information/content’ across the whole world which indicates that cultural values are also extended with the mass of information. Memes are regarded as multimodal texts which consist of letters and pictures from the linguistic point of view, and there is one term named ‘memefication’ which was suggested by Shifman [29, B.9] to the meme world. Appropriately, memefication denotes that as Shifman [29, B.10] declares ‘purely viral content probably does not exist - once a photo, or a video, reaches a certain degree of popularity on the Web, you can bet that someone, somewhere, will alter it’. According to this statement, once one meme becomes viral, it does not stay without being altered, and for this situation, Holm [16, B.5] represents the video ‘Charlie Bit My Finger’ as an example that was popular on You Tube in 2007, though firstly it was not a meme, just video, but this was altered to the meme by ‘remixing and mimicry respectively’. However, Mitman and Denham [26, B.34] et al. emphasize that as a result of memefication, memes can lose their original meaning and cultural influences, conversely their main function is to illustrate one specific national identity and cultural values, but rather they are being used as a marketing tool with the help of their social prominence. As media is the most powerful weapon for politics, another core function of memes is also criticizing political events or figures by the irony and satire which manifests the society’s attitude towards governmental issues in a polite and humorous way. Highfield [15, B.33] refers that memes are becoming a standard part of the political conversation for people who are engaged in politics and familiar with social media. In short, it is believed that memes are not just for fun, but they are becoming integral parts of political discourse. Also, Miltner [25, B.90] particularly focuses on memes’ remixing feature that assists the public to comprehend state affairs facilitated by well-known meme templates. Although Mitman and Denham [26, B.45] consider this aspect of memes is merely the tool for marketing, it is of paramount importance to enhance comprehensive knowledge structures on political and current news according to Miltner’s point of view. On the other hand, Denisova [8, B.52] warns that as it is uncontrollable to filter each idea on Social Media, memes can be used as a weapon for propaganda and distribute political misinformation due to information overload. Therefore, Denisova’s idea should be taken into consideration or critiques can be implemented by media reporters to increase political awareness of the society in spite of political benefits of Internet memes So, memes are not just a combination of visuals and words

to make humour, but they have an effective impact on politics, as it is also the part of media text.

Media language is incredibly diverse as it serves as a bridge for systematic discourse and public as well as its dynamic character demands for a regular research, particularly modern media texts. Fairclough [10, B.67] describes the aim of media language not just as reporting events to the audience, but it has a hybrid communicative function that combines official, public and personal registers: while official register is used to refer to formal events, public language might put into service in order to make media context understandable for all by using linguistic choices that are commonplace. He also argues that media language does not solely influence social event – quite the contrary – it can actively shape what is happening in reality: usage of impactful words, structures, manipulative phrases, emotional expressions – they all contribute to form conceptual world picture among receivers. Bell [3, B.72] also agrees this theory that media language is more than reporting, and it is not just an informative act, but interpretative communication as well, because beyond informing it might offer particular suggestions and viewpoints. In addition to this, media creators deliberately choose influential word expressions in order to profoundly affect to the addressee and his or her ideology about the reality. Several scholars, including van Dijk, Jakobson, Halliday and others classify pivotal communicative objectives of media texts. In particular, according to Jakobson and Bell informative function is the most primary aim of media communication, since it provides facts, important information with clarity and adequacy. Traditional media is almost based on factuality, and after the development of media discourse other functions found their importance as well, so whenever imagine traditional media tool, like radio, newspapers or television, the first thing comes to the mind is factual information, numbers, news and etc. On the other hand, van Dijk and Fairclough agree the idea of that simply informing cannot deeply introduce the notion of ‘media language’, so persuasive aim of media texts is also of utmost importance in constructing public interpretation through lexical units. Besides, media primarily relies on persuasiveness to effectively inform and influence society as well as it can help to build trust between the sender and receiver. It is clear that people always chase emotions during their whole life, and mostly try to take feelings from every part of their moments, that is why media texts also apply emotiveness to make messages more relatable, memorable and ultimately, persuasive. Moreover, emotive function, supported by Jakobson and Dobrosklonskaya, assists to exert an emotional impact and empathy on the audience. It is clear that people always chase emotions during their whole life, and mostly try to take feelings from every part of their moments, that is why media texts also apply emotiveness to make messages more relatable, memorable and ultimately, persuasive. Accordingly, Fairclough notes that evaluative character of media texts can allow media representatives to express judgement with the help of modality, connotative phrases. This aspect of media texts can provide the audience opportunity to deeply analyze, critical framing to understand the significance of information and form informed opinions about the world around them. Collectively, all these objectives manifest that media is not just a neutral indication of reality, but a deliberate linguistic form, formulated to inform, persuade, emote and evaluate at all. As all these functions are carried out through verbal signs, we will observe how language is used in media discourse to complete the aims.

Initially, traditional media texts identical to newspapers, magazines, television and radio broadcasts usually tend to have systematic and formalized structures that follow the norms of

standard grammar and stylistic accuracy. In fact, Bell [3, B.84] suggests that news media style has to balance both factuality and entertainment which demonstrates that this style is expected to be informative and attractive at the same time. However, it might trigger specific issues to balance them; therefore it is achieved with the assistance of well-structured sentences, short clauses or rhetorical devices like parallelism, antithesis and inversion which intensify rhythm and memorability. Overall, syntactical character of media texts includes several aspects: sentence type, phrase structures, tenses and voices. For example, *'Dozens Are Dead and Dozens More Missing as Catastrophic Rains Devastate Mexico'* – this headline is a complex sentence in active voice which consists of two main clauses (1st clause: Dozens are dead; 2nd clause: Dozens more missing), linked with conjunction ('and') and one subordinate clause (as catastrophic rains devastate Mexico) which indicates the reason for the events described in main clauses. Additionally, three different types of phrases are used: noun phrase (dozens, dozens more), verb phrases (are dead, missing, devastate) and prepositional phrase (as catastrophic rains devastate Mexico) as well as the omission of 'are' can be seen in the second clause, creating a slightly elliptical structure. It can be shortly concluded that to grab audience's attention and affect various syntactical structures should be used. Moreover, no less important are lexemes in shaping cognitive worldview on human's mind. In particular, a lexical feature of conventional media is the same as its syntaxes as it also requires materials with clarity, adequacy and objectivity, particularly terminologies are ubiquitous in old media discourse, since media can inform on any type of fields, namely science, sport, medicine. Let's observe the following fragment taken from both English and Uzbek newspapers: "After a quiet summer, the virus is hitting poultry flocks hard in the run-up to the holidays – and in the midst of a federal government shutdown"; "Shifokorning so'zlariga ko'ra, mazkur dori GLP-1 gormoni (ovqatdan keyin ichakda ishlab chiqiladigan gormon) ta'sirini taqlid qiladi. Bu gormon miyaga ta'sir qilib, insonda to'yinganlik hissini paydo qiladi." They are medical contexts that include special medical terminology: virus, poultry flocks in English; shifokor, dori, GLP-1 gormoni, ichak, miya in Uzbek, and it means that in both languages it is terminology which can preserve and organize texts in special fields. Beyond that borrowings are also of huge significance in old media as a result of social, political and cultural shifts in a language and then lexical exchanges happened. Indeed, English typically borrowed from German, French, Latin and Greek, therefore it is usual to see these type of words both in colloquial speech and mass media at the same time: "Every autumn, this wild and pristine pocket of the northeastern US puts on a dazzling display, as the Adirondacks' millions of trees transform into a veritable kaleidoscope of russet red, fiery yellow and burnt orange hues in one of the country's most dramatic leaf-peeping shows." This example is taken from one of the articles of BBC News on travel, and it can be seen that 'pristine' (from French), 'veritable' (from French) and 'kaleidoscope' (from Greek) are borrowings that are regular lexemes of traditional media texts.

On the other hand, lexicology of conventional media is a complex phenomenon somehow as scholars do have paradoxical ideas on the word usage in traditional media. In fact, Bell [3, B.86] defines traditional journalism as the notion which is predominantly based on neutral and formal style, excluding stylistic devices. Similarly to this idea, Reah [29, B.32] emphasizes that news media type requires journalists to be careful while picking each linguistic choices to fit a target pragmatic intention. In other words, the utmost important factor in traditional media's word usage is communicative aim, so news media style aims to inform and report news to receivers

through neutral lexical sources. However, this does not mean that stylistically marked vocabulary is not used in mass media; especially without evaluative and emotive words it is difficult to catch addressees' attention in headlines, newspaper or magazine articles, advertisements or editorials. The usage of metaphors, adjective or evaluative words may help readers to evoke feelings, deeply influence [31, B.228]. In addition to this, Fairclough [10, B.74] also criticizes that media communication cannot achieve its pragmatic intention without stylistically nuanced words, therefore it applies blended version of both formality and stylistics. For instance, in the headline of BBC (2023): 'Wildfires rage as heatwave grips Southern Europe' [32] – this can perform two communicative aims: inform and emotionally influence, since particular phrases such as 'wildfire rage', 'grips' create imaginary in readers' mind, reporting simultaneously. Thus, although traditional media text principally relies on objectivity, expressive means are also used to evoke emotion and enthusiasm. When it comes to semantic peculiarities of old media texts, synonyms, antonyms and polysemy are of great importance due to the fact that firstly in order to avoid repetition of words journalists address synonyms which lead to semantic clarity [3, B.102]. For example, in one article we can see various words with the same meaning: 'claim', 'declare', 'assert' or 'aytilishicha', 'ta'kidlanishicha', 'xabar berilishicha' in traditional Uzbek journalism, however these synonyms might differ in accordance with some nuances and degrees. On the contrary, lexemes with opposite meanings may affect, enhance critical analysis and shape the world conception of readers. Beyond these, antonyms highly contribute to cohesion of media texts, guiding the reader [14, B.38]. In particular, such newspaper headlines – 'The Guardian view on hope and despair in Gaza' and 'Jaholatga qarshi ma'rifat' – take charge of vividly conceptualizing the situations in reality, and in those the antonyms 'hope' and 'despair', 'jaholat' va 'ma'rifat' perform the same. Lastly, media personnel are disposed to use polysemantic words in spite of the fact that they might trigger ambiguity while decoding the message. On the other hand, polysemy plays a vital role in saving words, called linguistic economy, because one term can refer to different, but associative meanings, and with one word multiple interpretations may be delivered [3, B.29]: "The rose field by Philip Pullman – nail-biting conclusion to the Northern Lights series'. In this title, the phrase 'nail-biting' causes the creation of imagery even though 'nail' is not used as its literal meaning, but it generates an emotional adjective. Additionally, this phenomenon can occur in Uzbek mass media as well: 'kasb va ixtisosliklar sun'iy intellekt qo'lga o'tadi' – this division illustrates that 'qo'l' is a hand, and 'qo'lga o'tmoq' means to control, and polysemantic feature of words help to deliver the message as an intended way. In a real sense, all peculiarities of old journalism serve to make the context understandable, informative and emotional at the same time, so in order to keep this balance journalists should pay attention word choices.

Beyond traditional journalism modern media also has unique features in making media texts. In today's world contemporary audience's preferences have seen a shift from long reading to brevity, new media type is adjusting to such requirements, and therefore most websites and Social Media posts are trying to keep conciseness for users. As a result, modern journalism owns remarkably short syntactical structures, using elliptical and brief sentences, noun phrases. The increased adoption of new media platforms is mostly characterized by its informal and appealing syntax. Ellipsis, omitting some sentence components, like auxiliary verbs, articles and even subjects, can be mostly seen in Social Media post comments: 'unbelievable!', 'Cannot

believe this happened' (comments from BBC News Instagram profile), or in Uzbek Instagram posts ellipsis is used with adjectives for the most of time without any subjects or predicates: 'Juda ayanchli', 'Qiziq ekan'. In addition, hashtags can provide content-creators with an organized and accessible structure, and make easy find related posts for the audience. Hashtag structures are significantly concise and may sound as motivations and mottos as well. Semantically, digital media communication has a polysemic behavior alike conventional media texts, and meaning is verbalized by the means of evaluative adjectives at all. Moreover, Thurlow et al. [30, B.81] highlight that digital media texts can be decoded with the assistance of both verbal and multimodal signs, otherwise semantic misunderstandings might occur. According to lexicology, modern media noticeably differs from traditional media, since the usage of slangs, colloquial speech, non-verbal signs is considered normal unlike the latter media type. In other words, digital media is more powerful media representative than old media communication, thus new media requires users to be aware of particular culture in order not to across with cultural misinterpretations. As this paper mainly emphasizes the character of memes, its role and function in media, we would rather discuss memes' lexical peculiarities than other media types. Generally, Internet memes are often expressed by linguistic, including word, word combinations or linguoculturemes and non-linguistic signs (famous pictures, photos or videos). According to Ashurova et al. [1, B.56], linguoculturemes, in contradistinction to usual words, convey cultural meaning and can be verbalized as a word, word combination, paragraph or whole text, and seen in the following sources: myths, speech behavior, realias, literature, history, religion, etc. Across cultures, linguoculturemes can be varied: Halloween has a specific value in English nation, while Navruz is a unique ritual of Uzbek culture. They are widely used in the meme culture in order to illustrate one specific society's values and customs by adding the sense of humor. Holm [16, B.9] notes the saying "Keep calm and Carry on" as a sample that supports the above-mentioned idea due to the fact that this expression has a historical value since it was used as a motivational poster in Britain during the World War I, but there is a marked contrast between the original and current meanings of this poster. In fact, this phrase is humorously and ironically utilized today: "Keep calm and Order pizza" or "Keep calm and Blame the dog". Evidently, there is a paradoxically semantic shift between the original one and currents, as the initial idea suggested to take responsibility, whereas modern meanings are ignoring this. Ultimately, linguoculturemes are widely accepted to the meme culture as a verbalization of nationally specific ethics on media. Beyond that, neologisms, hashtags, irony and sarcasm are widely used in generating Internet memes in both English and Uzbek media discourse.

Interestingly, both conventional and modern media texts have another common peculiarity is that in all types of media texts it is not significant what is explicitly said, but what is implied in the delivered message is the priority, and for this aim, principles of Maxims theory is basic knowledge. Specifically, this theory was introduced by Paul Grice in his work "Logic and Conversation" in 1975. The main reason of these principles appearance is that which rules should be followed by the speaker and listener to achieve effective communication, and accordingly they are four – Maxims of Quality, Quantity, Relevance and Manner. Although Grice attempted to apply this theory into casual conversation, they are also related to media discourse as well. For example, newspaper and magazine headlines commonly tend to violate Maxim of Quantity, because more limited phrases are used than required. Besides, Maxim of

Quality can be broken if untruthful information or expressions are utilized as advertisements do in order to capture the audience's attention, however they do not always provide correct information, addressing to hyperbole, exaggeration and metaphor which evoke doubts on products. It is also noteworthy that memes often flout Maxim of Relevance to render the context rich of humor, irony, sarcasm and implicature at the same time. Accordingly, flouting of Maxims can effectively contribute the interpretation and emotiveness of media language.

Having examined both traditional and modern media texts in this study, it becomes evident that language lies at the heart of how communication adapts to social and technological change, and it is not for nothing that a language is an integral part of culture significantly. In traditional media, such as newspapers, television and radio, language tends to follow special norms of clarity and formality. As Fairclough [10, B.64] and van Dijk [31, B.174] observe, such texts usually rely on grammatical accuracy and neutral vocabulary to sustain public trust and objectivity. Modern media, on the other hand, manifests a very different linguistic dynamic. Online platforms such as Instagram, Twitter and Telegram are characterized by brevity, colloquial vocabulary and interactive tone. The presence of slang, memes, emojis and hybrid linguistic forms illustrates how language in digital contexts becomes a tool for humour, creativity and identity [6, B.14; 29, B.37]. This tendency can also be observed in Uzbek online communication where users freely combine English and Uzbek expressions to produce playful and culturally resonant meanings. Despite their contrast, both forms of media share one central function – to connect people through meaning. Traditional media achieves this through linguistic stability and authority; modern media achieves it through speed, emotion, and participation. Together, they reveal that the study of media language remains essential for understanding how culture, humour and social identity are constructed in contemporary communication. Besides, it should be identified that while conventional media intends to inform and report, based on objectivity, digital media communication has a different communicative aim: offering interactive and diverse aspects to users, focusing on cultural identities. Most importantly, violation of Maxim principles is one of the main factors in appropriately performing those pragmatic intentions.

In summary, both modern and traditional media texts play a pivotal role in shaping conceptual world picture on people's mind and influencing cultural expression. While conventional media is counted as a structural, standardized and formal discourse, reflecting cultural habits and social roles, contemporary media is introduced as the most effective and understandable method for informing and encoding information to the society, even manipulating. Most importantly, it should be emphasized that beyond just notifying the audience about news, or performing other speech act types, the role of media in political discourse is paramount noticeable. However, most people do not desire to be aware of political news via traditional media, like newspapers or television, instead, receiving a political message in a humorous or ironical way via Social medias or other new media styles is preferred. Internet memes are incomparable according to that idea, because not only might they share with the most engaging contents, but it is memes which make politics easier to understand. Consequently, media texts are not used for just transmitting information, perversely, they convey cultural and social connotation with linguistic signs that indicate cultural values (realia, phraseological units, slangs, colloquialism and etc.) and non-linguistics indications (fragments from national movies or programs, historical and cultural characters, symbols).

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